

STUDY OF THE CHEMICAL AND PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF GYPSUM MINERALS FROM DEPOSITS IN THE USTYURT REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN

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The production of gypsum binders is the most efficient in technical and economic terms, especially in terms of the specific costs of raw materials, fuel, electricity and labor per unit of product. There are also unlimited reserves of raw natural raw materials, as well as by-products of gypsum-containing materials for the production of gypsum and anhydrite binders. These include natural two-water gypsum, anhydrite, clay-gypsum, as well as industrial waste consisting mainly of two-water or anhydrous calcium sulfate or a mixture of them. [1]

Natural two-water gypsum (gypsum stone) is a rock of sedimentary origin, composed mainly of large or small crystals of two – water calcium sulfate $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. According to the appearance and structure of the rock, there are transparent crystalline gypsum, gypsum spar, fine-fiber gypsum with a silky sheen (selenite) and granular gypsum. The purest kind of granular gypsum, resembling marble in appearance, is sometimes called alabaster. The average density of gypsum stone depends on the amount and type of impurities and is 2.2-2.4 g/cm³.

Natural anhydrite is a rock of sedimentary origin, consisting mainly of anhydrous calcium sulfate CaSO_4 . Anhydrite is a rock more durable and dense than two-water gypsum. Its true density reaches 2.9-3.1 g/cm³, pure white anhydrite, but depending on the impurities, it, like gypsum, has different shades. In nature, anhydrite is less common than dihydrous gypsum [2].

As already noted earlier, gypsum minerals are the basis for obtaining binders for various purposes. Therefore, research is being conducted to obtain binders of various purposes that are competitive with imported analogues on the basis of local raw materials of Karakalpakstan. For these purposes, gypsum minerals from various deposits were selected and studied [1, 2, 3, 6].

The analysis of the chemical and mineralogical composition and physico-chemical properties of gypsum minerals allows us to choose a rational method

for obtaining binders for various purposes on their basis [11]. As a result of the conducted research, gypsum minerals of the Urge, Raushan, Aybuyir, Beltau, Kuskhanatau and Khujakul deposits with a high content of calcium sulfate and a favorable geographical location were chosen as the basis of binders for further research.

Laboratory chemical tests of natural gypsum stone were carried out according to GOST 4013- 82 [4]. As the results of the chemical analysis show (Tab.1), a sample of gypsum taken from the Urge deposit (No. 1) contains small amounts of impurities and as a result is cleaner compared to the rest of the studied objects. The amounts of CaO, SO₃, H₂O are close to theoretical, the content of dihydrous sulfuric acid salt reaches 96%, which corresponds to the characteristics of gypsum, on the basis of which it is possible to produce gypsum binders with increased physical and mechanical properties for the porcelain, ceramic and medical industries.

Table 1.
Chemical analysis of gypsum minerals

Oxides		Deposit					
		Urge	Raushan	Aybuyir	Kuskhanata u	Beltau	Khujakul
Mass content in % for air-dry substance	SiO ₂	1,37	4,85	6,33	2,88	7,31	20,16
	TiO ₂	<0,01	0,035	0,051	0,015	0,019	0,15
	Al ₂ O ₃	<0,10	0,53	0,82	0,45	0,76	2,44
	Fe ₂ O ₃	0,17	0,31	0,40	0,25	0,27	1,08
	MgO	0,65	0,70	0,60	0,4	0,5	0,5
	MnO	<0,01	<0,01	<0,01	0,01	0,01	0,02
	CaO	31,66	31,40	29,16	30,51	29,16	23,97
	Na ₂ O	0,07	0,18	0,24	0,1	0,21	0,39
	K ₂ O	0,03	0,36	0,21	0,11	0,22	0,37
	P ₂ O ₅	0,053	0,048	0,05	0,048	0,042	0,068
	SO ₃ , common	44,7	44,90	41,70	44,67	41,7	34,27
	SO ₃ ,sulfat e	44,52	41,52	41,18	44,61	41,5	32,9
L.D.C.	21,86	20,06	20,52	20,49	19,9	17,91	

H ₂ O, 320° C	20,1	16,89	18,76	19,63	18,75	14,32
CO ₂	1,76	3,14	1,21	0,55	1,1	2,97

The sample of the Raushan deposit (No. 2) has almost no impurities, the amounts of CaO, SO₃, H₂O contained in it are close to the theoretical and reach 93%. The 4-sample taken from the Kuskhanatau deposit, which contains approximately 93-94% of the dihydrous sulfuric acid salt, has a similar chemical composition.

The gypsum sample of the Aibuyir deposit (No. 3) contains a large amount of clay mineral impurities, therefore it differs from the first object by low CaO and SO₃ contents. The total content of the dihydrous sulfuric acid salt CaSO₄·2H₂O is 89%. On the basis of such minerals, it is possible to obtain gypsum and building materials with increased physical and mechanical properties for the construction industry.

The sample from the Beltau deposit (No. 5), as well as No. 3, contains to a large extent impurities in the form of clay substances, therefore it differs in a relatively small content of CaO and SO₃. The total content of the dihydrous sulfuric acid salt CaSO₄·2H₂O is 89.5%. This mineral belongs to the gypsum rock of the second grade, in industry, gypsum and building materials with increased physical and mechanical properties are produced on its basis.

Sample No. 6 from the Khujakul deposit contains large amounts of clay impurities, differs in a small content of CaO and SO₃. The total content of the dihydrous sulfuric acid salt CaSO₄·2H₂O is 68.4%. This mineral belongs to the gypsum rock of the fourth grade, therefore, it is possible to obtain gypsum and building materials with increased physical and mechanical properties on its basis.

A comprehensive study of the mineralogical compositions of gypsum minerals was carried out by X-ray, thermogravimetric, microscopic and spectral analysis methods. These analyses are universal and by now more advanced methods for studying the compositions of solid materials [5, 7].

The high diffusivity of the lines in the region of valence and deformation vibrations in the structure of the hydroxide ion and the water molecule indicates the presence of both adsorption and chemically bound crystallization water in the compositions of gypsum minerals.

Based on the above data on the chemical and mineralogical composition, it can be concluded that gypsum minerals of Karakalpakstan can be considered as a basis for obtaining binders for various purposes.

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